

РАЗДЕЛ. ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8052730>

УДК 644.1

HEAT RECOVERY OF VENTILATION EMISSIONS AS ONE OF THE WAYS TO IMPROVE THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

S.S. Putilov,

CEO, senior expert,
EnergExpert Group LLC
Moscow

Annotation: The article analyzes the ways of reconstruction of existing buildings with a simultaneous increase in their energy efficiency and extension of their service life. A set of works has been defined to ensure the extension of the life cycle of buildings while ensuring strict energy efficiency standards. Based on the results of the article, an assessment is made of some measures to improve energy efficiency and the concept of "energy efficient reconstruction" is formed.

Keywords: energy efficiency, heat loss, heat recovery, renovation, wall insulation, systems, savings, resources, environment, environmental engineering

УТИЛИЗАЦИИ ТЕПЛОТЫ ВЕНТИЛЯЦИОННЫХ ВЫБРОСОВ КАК ОДНИ ИЗ ПУТЕЙ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭНЕРГОЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ЖИЛЫХ ЗДАНИЙ

С.С. Путилов,

генеральный директор, главный эксперт,
ООО «ЭнергоЭксперт Групп»,
г. Москва

Аннотация: В статье анализируются пути реконструкций действующих зданий с одновременным повышением их

энергоэффективности и продлением срока их эксплуатации. Определен комплекс работ для обеспечения продления жизненного цикла зданий при обеспечении строгих норм энергоэффективности. По итогам статьи дана оценка некоторым мерам повышения энергоэффективности и формируется понятие «энергоэффективная реконструкция».

Ключевые слова: энергоэффективность, потери тепла, утилизация тепла, реконструкция, утепление стен, системы, экономия, ресурсы, окружающая среда, экологическая инженерия

Introduction. The concept of energy efficiency is inextricably linked to the rational consumption of resources. If we talk about residential buildings, then we are primarily talking about the consumption of thermal and electrical energy. The question of achieving justified efficiency in the consumption of energy resources remains relevant. Its solution is inextricably linked with the level of technology and technology development, with the use of modern building materials and other factors.

When talking about improving the energy efficiency of buildings, houses, we often talk about energy conservation. This term here is not quite correct, since "energy conservation" is more associated with a reduction in consumption. The concept of "energy efficiency" implies conservation of allocated energy, which is associated primarily with the creation of comfortable conditions in the building for people. And only in the second turn it is supposed not to allow additional energy consumption.

Ways to improve energy efficiency. In determining the ways of heat loss from a building, several such sources are named, which can be placed in the following order of importance:

1. Losses through the facades of buildings. It is solved by insulating the facades from the outside and creating comfortable conditions inside. The process of insulation is in the position a little more from the initial.
2. Losses depending on the construction of the building [1].
3. Window structures. Replacing windows with energy efficient windows. "Energy-saving windows show their effectiveness in reducing utility costs for residential and commercial buildings." [2, p. 15].

4. Utilization of heat of ventilation emissions. It can be argued that such an uncomplicated process at non-industrial level – in administrative buildings and facilities, buildings of domestic complex practically has not been carried out.

5. Utilization of wastewater heat. Possible savings are comparable to the savings from air recycling [3].

6. According to various estimates, heat losses through the ventilation system of natural inducement account for up to 50 % of all such losses [4].

At the same time, the issue of utilization of ventilation emissions is the least expensive in terms of technical modernization. And such renovation can be done both in conjunction with the insulation of facades, and as an independent measure.

Incoming cold air into the building from outside passes through a rotating rotary recuperator. As it passes through, heat is exchanged with the removed air through adjacent walls. As a result of the heat exchange, the difference between the two contacted streams will be at 5-6 degrees [5].

Thus, the heating system will not produce heating of cold air, but with a temperature of 15-16 ° C to a comfortable value. In doing so, it will be correct to state:

- the incoming air will be fresh;
- there will be no change in the humidity of the air during heat exchange;
- disease-causing organisms, harmful gases and odors will be removed from the room.

Figure 1 – The principle of operation of the heat recovery unit of ventilation emissions

Evaluation characteristics of the measures.

Evaluate the effectiveness of implementation of the system of heat recovery of ventilation emissions can be estimated by the following algorithm:

Let's estimate the amount of supply air heated by the heating system of the building. Let's take into account that this heated air will be subsequently removed into the atmosphere [6].

Then for a period of 1 day for a typical residential building we get:

$$V^{h_{vent.}} = 3600 \times \tau \times \sum_{i=1}^m A_i \cdot V_i.$$

where A_i – exhaust vent area, m^2 ;

V_i – average exhaust air velocity, m/s ;

m – total number of shafts;

i – shafts number.

τ – testing period, 24 h.

Then for a typical residential building we get the value:

$$V^{h_{vent.}} = 3600 * 24 * \sum_{i=1}^m 0,116 * 0,29 = 1046338,56 \text{ m}^3.$$

Having this value, we can calculate the amount of energy consumed for heating the supply air heated by the ventilation system for the day.

1. We will proceed from the following input data presented in Table

Table 1 – Initial data for calculating energy for air heating

Indicator	Value	Note
Specific heat capacity of air, kJ/kg/°C	1,018	
Total floor area in the building	3477	According to the passport data of the building
Indoor air density at a given temperature, kg/m ³	1,182	
Average temperature over the test period (outdoors), °C	- 7,3	We purposely chose the cold period of the year, when more energy is spent on heating the air
Average temperature over the test period (indoor), °C	21,6	

Then let's determine the amount of energy used to heat the air according to the dependence:

$$Q_{\text{vent. system}} = \frac{c \cdot \rho \cdot (V_{\text{vent}} + V_{\text{smoke}})}{3600} \times (t_{\text{in}} - t_{\text{out}}) =$$

$$\frac{1,018 \cdot 1,182 \cdot (1046338,56 + 209268)}{3600} \times (21,6 - (-7,3)) = 12\,128,69 \text{ kW}$$

where $V_{\text{vent.}}$ and V_{smoke} are the volume of air removed through the shaft ducts of the ventilation and smoke removal system.

If we take into account the 40 % savings value when introducing a heat recovery unit into the design, the possible thermal efficiency for the building will be up to 4.85 (rounded up) thousand kW [7].

Conclusions. One of the promising areas of improving energy efficiency of buildings is the utilization of ventilation emissions. At the same time this system is relevant for all buildings in operation. It is possible to install a simple heat exchanger in buildings that have previously

experienced insulation of the facade of the building and replacement of windows, as well as for buildings that have not been previously subjected to reconstruction.

Bibliography

[1] A.A. Grigorieva, A.A. Zarubina, M.F. Makeev Influence of the form of the residential building on the size of heatlosses. – 2016. №3-4 (24-25). 8-13 с.

[2] Putilov S.S. Energy-saving windows as a way to reduce costs / S.S. Putilov // Actual Studies. – 2023. № 19-1(149). 13-15 с. – DOI 10.51635/27131513_2023_19_1_13. – EDN KLMEOG.

[3] Method of utilization of low-potential heat of domestic wastewater: Patent for invention No. 2243460 RF, F25B30/00. /DG. Zakirov, I.I. Borinskikh, A.V. Aksinov.

[4] Methodology of full-scale thermal tests for instrumental determination of energy consumption of buildings put into operation and evaluation of their compliance with the energy efficiency requirements. Base of normative documents:: from 15.05.2023 [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://goo.su/NUBTjM> (date of access: 05/12/2023)

[5] Saibel A.V. Energy-saving technologies in construction // Engineering Vestnik Don. – 2012. 205 с.

[6] Danilevsky L.N. Method of calculating the economic feasibility of energy efficiency measures / L.N. Danilevsky // Building Science and Technology. – 2009. № 6. 12-17 с.

[7] Danilevsky, L.N. Technical solutions and terms of reference for the development of the relevant part of the design and estimate documentation regarding the implementation of measures and placement of equipment to improve energy efficiency in the pilot buildings: [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://energoeffect.gov.by/effbuild/download/89.pdf> (date of access: 05/12/2023)

Список литературы (перевод)

[1] Григорьева А.А., Зарубина А.А., Макеев М.Ф. Влияние формы жилого дома на величину теплопотерь. – 2016. №3-4 (24-25). 8-13 с.

[2] Путилов С.С. Энергосберегающие окна как способ снижения затрат / С.С. Путилов // Актуальные исследования. – 2023. № 19-1(149). 13-15 с. – DOI 10.51635/27131513_2023_19_1_13. – ЭДН КЛМЕОГ.

[3] Способ утилизации низкопотенциальной теплоты хозяйственно-бытовых сточных вод: Патент на изобретение № 2243460 РФ, F25B30/00. /ДГ. Закиров, И.И. Боринских, А.В. Аксинов.

[4] Методика проведения натуральных тепловых испытаний для инструментального определения энергопотребления вводимых в эксплуатацию зданий и оценки их соответствия требованиям энергоэффективности. База нормативных документов:: от 15.05.2023 [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <https://goo.su/NUBTjM> (дата обращения: 12.05.2023)

[5] Сайбель А.В. Энергосберегающие технологии в строительстве // Инженерный вестник Дона. – 2012. 205 с.

[6] Данилевский Л.Н. Методика расчета экономической целесообразности мероприятий по энергоэффективности / Л.Н. Данилевский // Строительная наука и техника. – 2009. № 6. 12-17 с.

[7] Данилевский, Л.Н. Технические решения и техническое задание на разработку соответствующей части проектно-сметной документации в части реализации мероприятий и размещения оборудования по повышению энергоэффективности в пилотных зданиях: [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <https://energoeffect.gov.by/effbuild/download/89.pdf> (дата обращения: 12.05.2023)

© S.S. Putilov, 2023

Поступила в редакцию 11.05.2023

Принята к публикации 18.05.2023

Для цитирования:

Putilov S.S. Heat recovery of ventilation emissions as one of the ways to improve the energy efficiency of residential buildings // Инновационные научные исследования. 2023. № 5-3(29). С. 11-17. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>